

The Use of Daratumumab in Relapsed Refractory Multiple Myeloma and Clinical Experience:
Letter to the Editor

Editorial Letter

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Keywords: Relapsed Refractory Multiple Myeloma, Daratumumab, Survival

Letter

In the treatment of multiple myeloma (MM), the use of proteasome inhibitors (PIs) and immunomodulatory (IMiD) agents has led to increased survival times; however, in Relapsed Refractory Multiple Myeloma (RRMM) patients, there are patients resistant to both PIs and IMiDs. The prognosis for these patients is poor, with a median overall survival (OS) of approximately 8-9 months. Therefore, new treatment options are required for MM. Daratumumab, the first of its classes, is a human IgG kappa monoclonal antibody developed against CD38. The SIRIUS phase II study showed that daratumumab monotherapy achieved a 29% overall response rate (ORR) in a group of RRMM patients who had received a median of five prior lines of therapy (1). Its efficacy in combination therapies has also been evaluated in the CASTOR and POLLUX studies. The CASTOR study found that adding daratumumab to bortezomib-dexamethasone (Vd) in RRMM patients prolonged OS and reduced the risk of death by 26% compared to Vd after a median follow-up of 72.6 months (2). In the POLLUX study, the combination of daratumumab with lenalidomide-dexamethasone (Rd) significantly

prolonged OS compared to Rd and provided a 27% reduction in the risk of death at a median follow-up of 79.7 months (3). Studies showing increased survival rates have commonly reported infusion-related reactions. Consequently, the COLUMBA study compared the intravenous and subcutaneous forms of the drug in terms of both efficacy and pharmacokinetic properties, demonstrating equivalence. In addition, higher patient satisfaction and a significant reduction in infusion-related reactions were observed with the subcutaneous formulation (4). The APOLLO study investigated survival with subcutaneous use of pomalidomide and daratumumab, another IMiD. The results of this study showed that the combination of subcutaneous daratumumab and pomalidomide dexamethasone improved progression-free survival (PFS) compared with pomalidomide dexamethasone alone (5).

Dear Editor, we observed that daratumumab provided a survival advantage in the RRMM patient group with low survival rates. Its use in combination therapies with bortezomib from PIs and lenalidomide and pomalidomide from IMiDs has resulted in increased in both overall and progression-free survival. Although drug-related

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reactions were more common with the intravenous formulation, as shown in previous studies, we did not encounter them with the subcutaneous formulation. The subcutaneous formulation also facilitates ease of administration and patient compliance. Adverse events that developed with the use of the drug were managed according to standard care protocols. Our experience supports daratumumab as an effective and reliable treatment option based on real-world data.

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Cite: Oral, K. (2026). Use of Daratumumab in Relapsed Refractory Multiple Myeloma and Clinical Experience. *Acta Medica Young Doctors*, 2(1), 35–36.

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